

The Potential of Magnetometry to Survey Iberian Sites: Revealing the Hidden Urbanism of 'Kelin'

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The Site

The ancient city of Kelin is located in a hillfort near the municipality of Caudete de las Fuentes, in the Utiel-Requena district (Valencia, Spain).

The extensive chronology of Kelin expands from the beginning of the Iron Age (about 680 B.C.) to ibero-roman times (75 B.C.). Kelin became the capital of a large Iberian territory and developed its own coinage (2nd century B.C.).

Some studies have suggested that the site was destroyed as a result of a corrective measure applied by Rome to those Iberian cities that supported the defeated Sertorian side during the civil war.

The twenty three excavation campaigns carried out by the University of Valencia between 1956 and 2002 have focused on two main areas at the site (in blue, right) containing a number of houses, covering a total of 1000 m².

In December 2013 a magnetometer survey was undertaken at the non-excavated area of the protected site (in red, left) in order to map other potential structures.

Fourteen survey grids of ~20m x 20m (in green, left) were surveyed covering an area of ~4.600 m².

Data Collection & Processing

A team of three people collected the data during two days of fieldwork, using a Bartington 601 fluxgate gradiometer. The instrument measures variations in the vertical component of the magnetic field. It has two sensors, one positioned 1m above the other. The difference in the output of the two sensors represents the magnetic gradient; variations in the background field (common to both sensors) are removed by subtraction.

The raw data was processed using the Geoplot software (Geoscan Research version 3.0). ArcMap (ArcGIS) was used to georeference the images produced with Geoplot and to carry out the interpretation of the data.

Anomaly Interpretation

The survey revealed a series of both strong magnetic responses and linear positive and negative magnetic anomalies covering the whole area surveyed.

The anomalies seem to indicate the location of square and rectangular houses aligned along a series of perpendicular and longitudinal negative or weakly positive magnetic responses which may show the distribution of roads or perimetral walls.

The intensity of the strong magnetic anomalies may be associated with substantial burnt features such as mud-brick walls or other structural materials of the houses. This interpretation would seem to agree with the possible final destruction of the site. Other linear negative magnetic anomalies may be produced by the mud-brick walls that were not affected by the fire or the contrast produced by stone foundations of the houses.

— Linear (positive & negative) magnetic anomalies indicating the location of possible buried structures
 ■ Strong magnetic anomalies of possible structural burned material
 ■ Magnetic disturbance produced by surface metallic objects

Conclusions

The approach used in this study has proved the great potential of magnetometer survey to map the urban layout of Iberian sites with a final destruction phase in a non-invasive and cost-effective manner. Two days' survey and a small team were enough to get a complete view of the buried structures at the site and therefore, an approximation of how Kelin looked like before its destruction. Further work intends to use other geophysical techniques at the site to complement the magnetic results in the non-excavated area. For example, ground-penetrating radar may provide further details on some of the internal structures or information about the depth of burial of the structures.

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